

**Facilitating secure network communication with resource constrained
embedded devices: Analysis and implementation of local web control
in smart home applications**

Master's Thesis

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Master of Engineering

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Abstract

Modern smart home IoT (Internet of Things) devices are commonly controlled with proprietary mobile applications via remote servers, which can have significant adverse implications for the end user. This work aims to analyze the feasibility of an alternative method of control fully within the local network of the user, leveraging existing standard web technologies and open control interfaces to enable a maximum degree of privacy, choice and sustainability within the smart home ecosystem, while ensuring the system remains secure against unauthorized manipulation. Given that a large quantity of IoT devices in use today are limited in their computational resources, both in the amount of memory available as well as the processing speed, standard approaches such as employing HTTPS-based transport security are not always feasible and the need for alternative solutions that are more suitable for such constrained devices becomes apparent. Herein, multiple approaches for achieving lightweight and secure web-based device control are outlined and compared. Subsequently, a demonstrator control system architecture using keyed message authentication codes is implemented. This proof-of-concept shows that it is feasible to meet essential security objectives in a local web IoT control context while utilizing less than a kilobyte of additional memory compared to an unsecured solution; thus promoting sustainability through hardening the control protocols used by existing devices that previously had serious security flaws, but too little resources for implementing standard web cryptography. Therefore this work contributes to the achievement of the vision of a fully open and secure local smart home.

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List of Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Explanation
AES	Advanced Encryption Standard
AP	Access Point
API	Application Programming Interface
ASIC	Application Specific Integrated Circuit
CA	Certificate Authority
DDoS	Distributed Denial of Service
ESP	A series of network-enabled microcontrollers by Espressif Systems
GDPR	(European Union) General Data Protection Regulation
GPU	Graphics Processing Unit
HMAC	Hash-Based Message Authentication Code
HTML	Hypertext Markup Language
HTTP	Hypertext Transfer Protocol
HTTPS	Hypertext Transfer Protocol Secure
ID	Identification/Identifier
IoT	Internet of Things
IP(v4)	Internet Protocol (version 4)
JS	JavaScript
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation
MAC	Message Authentication Code
MitM	Man-in-the-Middle
NIST	(United States) National Institute of Standards and Technology
NTP	Network Time Protocol
OTA	Over-the-air (software update)
PaaS	Platform-as-a-Service
PBKDF2	Password-based Key Derivation Function 2
PKI	Public Key Infrastructure
PQC	Post-Quantum Cryptography
PSK	Pre-Shared Key
PWA	Progressive web app
RNG	Random Number Generator

SDK	Software Development Kit
SHA	Secure Hash Algorithm
SSH	Secure Shell
TCP	Transmission Control Protocol
TLS	Transport Layer Security
UDP	User Datagram Protocol
UI	User Interface
URL	Uniform Resource Locator
WASM	WebAssembly
WLED	Wireless Lighting Effects Driver, an open source lighting control software for ESP microcontrollers
WS	WebSocket

1 Introduction

1.1 Motivation

In the last few years, Internet of Things (IoT) has been gaining significant traction and proliferation especially in domestic environments. Marketed as "Smart Home" systems, IoT platforms aim to automate the operation of common household appliances and make controlling them more convenient. IoT products targeted at the consumer market are typically connected via a remote cloud-hosted server, commonly run by the device manufacturer. These online services offer limited interfaces for the end user to control their devices - often no more than a manufacturer-provided proprietary smartphone app, sometimes accompanied by voice control services like Amazon Alexa. While this implementation - at least initially - satisfies the use cases of some customers, a multitude of users wish to control their devices fully locally within their own home network, without the need to connect to an external server hosted on the public Internet. Various reasons for this are outlined in the following section [1.1.1](#). However, most commercially available IoT devices do not offer such an application programming interface (API) to facilitate local control, instead running a closed-source device firmware that makes control possible solely via the aforementioned manufacturer cloud service and associated apps.

1.1.1 Reasons to opt for local IoT device control

There are a multitude of reasons why a user may prefer to control their devices locally, of which some of the most prominent are outlined below:

Firstly, all **security** considerations are constrained to the network to which the device is connected and its immediate physical vicinity. While refraining from connecting to any external server alone does not adequately protect a device, it significantly reduces the number of possible attack vectors. In practice, many remote IoT deployments - particularly those developed as cheaply as possible and those with previous generation devices with little ongoing support and low-end hardware - are remarkably insecure. For example, a cryptanalysis of the firmware used on IoT devices by the Platform-as-a-Service (PaaS) operator *Tuya* revealed that, among other flaws, they used unprotected plain HTTP messages to provision the device with secret keys, which successfully enabled the researcher to mount a Man-in-the-Middle (MitM) attack in order to

install arbitrary firmware on the device ([Ste18], timestamps 19:20 and 23:30). This ultimately led to the development of the *Tuya-Convert* tool, which facilitates wireless installation of alternative firmware on Espressif 8266-based Tuya devices. Although the security of Tuya-based devices has improved since, it is still impossible for end users or even their own customers (device vendors) to independently verify the security value of the solution due to the closed source ecosystem of this and similar IoT platforms. Tuya has since published a security whitepaper and claims to be in compliance with several standards and regulations, including *ISO 27001* and *ISO 27701* [Tuy], it is by no means guaranteed that the solution is completely secure given that the platform was marketed to feature "military-grade security" (cmp. [Ste18]) when the grave vulnerabilities were identified in 2018.

Even if a manufacturer takes care to implement state-of-the-art security measures, regular updates might not be provided down the line, or they may not be installed by users. Given that device firmware, the control software used on cloud servers and end-user apps are all commonly proprietary, it becomes impossible to independently ascertain that the application contains no critically exploitable bugs or even deliberate backdoors. In contrast, open source software allows the user to verify and - if desired - modify the codebase. This allows for independent review, thus it is not longer a necessity to put unconditional trust in the manufacturer - both in their ability to produce safe, bug-free code and in their benevolence - to allow their device to connect to one's internal network. However, even in the suboptimal case that device firmware is closed source, the existence of a feasible local control mechanism makes it possible to block the device from connecting to the Internet, which significantly limits the possible attack surface to exploit the device or even gain unauthorized access to the internal network itself.

Privacy is another common concern. Remotely controlled IoT devices usually require registering an account with the manufacturer, necessitating the disclosure of personally identifiable data, commonly at least an e-mail address. This puts the user at risk in the event the IoT control server is compromised. Particularly, their e-mail address might be exposed to third parties, which could lead to spam and phishing attacks. Ensuring an appropriate level of privacy protection is particularly essential with devices capable of recording and monitoring highly personal living spaces in a home, such as security cameras and voice assistants.

Furthermore, if storage in the server's database is not implemented according to best practices, the user's credentials - most commonly a password - might be trivial to obtain. This could lead to more important accounts being compromised if the user re-used the same password, which is unfortunately commonplace due to the high cognitive load associated with having to remember distinct passwords to potentially dozens of different services - also known as password fatigue.

A study on login credential databases publicly leaked between 2008 and 2016[WJH⁺18] indicate that 38% of users that had accounts on multiple of the 107 examined services re-used an identical password at least once across these services. As with security, efforts to verify that a device's behavior aligns with a manufacturer's privacy policy - or even becoming aware what data the device collects and sends to third parties in the first place - is significantly impeded by software being proprietary.

Another reason to prefer local control is **latency**. Sending a network packet within one's local network is typically accomplished within less than 50 ms , which feels instant to the user. Contrast this with a remote manufacturer server that may be in another country, where sending the same packet may take about half a second. The user-perceived responsiveness of the device is severely impacted, as the minimum perceivable latency is only 200 ms at most (cmp. [CMN83] p. 32).

Availability is another major concern. If the IoT control server is unreachable or the user's internet connection is disrupted, control of the devices is not possible.

Another essential factor is **longevity**. After an IoT product has reached the end of its commercial availability, the manufacturer might opt to disable servers or support for that device. This could also occur due to manufacturer bankruptcy. If the remote IoT control server ceases to function, the device is not controllable and depending on its design, severely limited in its functionality or rendered entirely inoperable. An example for this are home security cameras and systems by Nest Secure, which have been disabled in April 2024[Goo24]. Such shutdowns are not only costly for the user, since they have to replace the device, but it is also unsustainable for the environment to dispose of a device in physically perfect working order merely because the means of controlling it no longer function.

Flexibility is another advantage. With a sufficiently open local API, advanced automation via software like Home Assistant or other custom integrations becomes a straightforward possibility. Such options are typically severely limited with proprietary servers. This often results in vendor lock, where a user is unable to automate a process despite owning hardware that has the technical capability to do so. As a simple example, consider a motion detector and a light. If only one of these two devices uses a proprietary app and there is no way to interface with it over a common API or compatibility adapter, even a simple automation use case such as turning on the light if motion is detected can not be implemented using these components. This example highlights the importance of open - and preferably local - APIs, as they are a base prerequisite for effective home automation. Without such basic provisions for **interoperability**, deeming IoT devices "smart" may be considered an overstatement.

Remote access is one of the key reasons manufacturers often opt for preferring remote server control over local control. It is a selling point to be able to e.g. turn on the heat at home before one leaves work, or check that all the lights are off after leaving the house. However, remote and local control APIs are not mutually exclusive, so a decision to not offer a local API might be due to manufactures desiring a higher degree of control or reducing implementation complexity by foregoing the need for e.g. an embedded webserver on the device. Philips Hue is a positive example for a large scale IoT ecosystem that offers both remote and local APIs.

1.1.2 Methods to proliferate local control

In 2024, the *Open Home Foundation* was created to facilitate the goals of **privacy**, **choice** and **sustainability** (cmp. [Ope24]) with the vision of enabling a truly open and local smart home system. The WLED project, which will be used for the main example implementations in this work, is also a member of the Open Home Foundation.

Open source software is a key element in making IoT devices more accessible - including local control. When a device runs an open source firmware, users are free to customize its software behavior to their specific needs, which can include adding APIs to enable local control.

Consumer behavior is essential for a long-term improvement of implemented IoT solutions. If customers are sensitized to the issue and prefer purchasing devices that allow local control or are even fully open source, this is likely to influence manufacturer behavior to offer more flexible means to use their devices.

Web technology and in particular, JavaScript APIs present in modern browsers has evolved rapidly in the last few years, to the point where it is often feasible to replace proprietary native apps with open web-based apps that offer cross-platform compatibility with almost all Internet-connected end user devices that have a standard web browser installed. This could be expanded further in the future to offer built-in non-TLS means for browsers to communicate securely with low resource locally connected IoT devices.

1.2 Research Goal

The goal of this thesis is to identify and analyze several methods for offering a secure local means of control for IoT devices, with particular focus on browser-based web apps, i.e. without requiring the installation of custom software on client control devices. For implementation, the ESP8266 and ESP32 microcontrollers by Espressif are considered due to their widespread use both in home-made and commercial IoT devices. For demonstration, the author's open source lighting control project WLED is used, which is further described in section 2.7. As it would be beneficial to use the same security technology as the public Internet, adding transport layer security (TLS) capability to the embedded web server of IoT devices shall be considered.

This thesis has two research objectives. Firstly, the feasibility of running a full HTTPS/TLS server on the IoT device is analyzed. Secondly, alternative lightweight means of securing a control API are identified, particularly for devices that do not have sufficient resources to run a TLS server in a practical scenario.

1.3 Structure of the Thesis

Firstly, relevant requirements, mechanisms and the underlying theoretical fundamentals are described and analyzed. Next, the relevant empiric demonstrator implementation steps are outlined and described in detail. Finally the result of the Thesis is summarized and the completion of its research objectives is analyzed.

2 Fundamentals

In the following, fundamental concepts used for the subsequent implementation are outlined and the necessary prerequisites established, which encompass both the security objectives the solution aims to achieve as well as the possible ways to implement cryptographic protection measures in a web browser context.

2.1 Security objectives

Prior to designing and implementing any new network connected digital information system, careful consideration ought to be given to defining which types of both accidental misuse and malicious attacks the system should be resistant to. This is a foundational requirement for designing any system that is to be deemed "secure" by any reasonable definition. Different particular aspects of data and system protection are known as security objectives. A multitude of security objectives exist, though there are three core security objectives, namely Confidentiality, Integrity, and Authenticity (cmp. [PPG24]), which could be deemed to be the most essential in general cases.

The objective of **confidentiality** is ensuring data can only be read by the authorized parties, both in transmission and storage.

Integrity is concerned with attesting that the data has not been modified, for example during transmission. This includes both accidental modification, for instance due to bit flips and active (malicious) manipulation of the data.

Authenticity is a related concept to ascertain that the data was sent by a party who is permitted to do so.

Further objectives include availability and non-repudiation. Availability is a major concern in industrial and critical infrastructure for such systems where a service outage - for example due to the expiry of a trusted security certificate - would lead to commercial or even physical damage to users. This includes manufacturing plants, but also essential facilities like power systems equipment and transportation means such as elevators. Non-repudiation enables verification that the data indeed originated from the supposed sender and could not have been forged by the receiver or a third-party.

In home IoT contexts, integrity and authenticity are typically most essential for control of most device categories. Depending on the nature of the device, protection of confidentiality is also highly relevant though, especially regarding IoT devices capable of recording confidential or personally identifiable data, such as security cameras and voice control systems like Amazon Alexa. Disruptions in availability, while undesirable, typically pose little hazard and are thus regarded as a lower priority.

Consider a connected heater or pool pump that may be turned on and off via a phone app - there is little confidential information in the control command itself. However, consequences if the device is operated without the authorization and knowledge of the owner may be devastating - for example when a heater turns on that has been covered with textile.

2.2 Browser-based Cryptography

In order to successfully design a secure local IoT system controlled exclusively via a web app running in a standard browser, it is first necessary to gather an overview of the cryptographic functionalities present in modern browsers and their associated limitations.

2.2.1 Web-based apps as an alternative to native apps

The primary means of control for most commercially available IoT devices for home use are native smartphone applications. While major mobile operating system software development kits (SDKs) offer a high degree of flexibility for the application developer in the interfaces and device features they can utilize, they can have drawbacks for the end user. Since the source code is typically not accessible, users have to trust manufacturers and distributors not to abuse the power granted to them. Both modern operating systems and browsers implement a permission-based system to let the user decide which device functionality and data the app or website is allowed to access. A key problem with this permission system is that it is often not clear to the user why and in which scope particular permissions are required for the app to function. The choice given to them is often not granular enough. For example, a "Read and modify media stored on the device" permission may be used merely for exporting a local backup of the app configuration - on the other end of the spectrum, it could be used by a malicious app to retrieve all personal photos on the device and send them to an external server. Another specific example that is particularly applicable to IoT control apps is location access. Many Wi-Fi-based devices open a Wi-Fi access point (AP) for initial setup. The app then scans for Wi-Fi networks matching the SSID pattern

used by the device AP and connects to it to provision the device with the credentials for the user's home Wi-Fi network. In recent versions of Android it is required to grant the location permission to scan for and connect to Wi-Fi networks within the app, as network SSIDs could theoretically be referenced against publicly available SSID maps such as WiGLE and thus a likely location of the user inferred. Therefore, granting the location permission is often required for initial device setup to succeed. However, this has the side effect of allowing the app to store the location of the user during the setup process or even to continually track them, which constitutes data collection that for most categories of smart home devices (such as for example lights, air conditioning and cameras) is not strictly necessary for device functionality and thus not only fails to adequately protect the users privacy, but also risks not being in compliance with laws enacted to protect individual privacy, such as the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) in the EU. A prominent example of such overreaching data collection is the IoT platform by PaaS operator *Tuya* introduced above, that as of 2018, stored both the exact coordinates of the mobile device used at setup time as well as the device activity history and shared this information with the platform customer, i.e. in most cases the vendor of the IoT device. The scale of this issue is alarming, as the Tuya platform was used by more than 10.000 brands at the time and when inquired, Tuya representatives clarified that it is not possible even for the vendor themselves to limit this data collection, as "[storing this] basic but necessary information [in their cloud would be needed and] is avoidless [sic]". (cmp. [Ste18], timestamp 12:08-14:02)

If control of an IoT device from user end devices is desired without requiring the installation of additional apps, web browsers can be a viable choice. Virtually all computers and smartphones and sometimes even more specialized devices such as e-book readers come with modern browsers pre-installed. CSS offers a rich toolkit to create visually appealing user interfaces and JavaScript offers the majority of features needed to implement client-side logic - to the point that many natively installable apps are merely wrappers around a web page. This approach is used by the WLED project as well as other widely used applications such as the Discord chat platform. An even more lightweight alternative are progressive web apps (PWA), which appear like native apps to the user - for instance by having a dedicated app icon, running full-screen without visible browser UI, and being able to run offline using caching[MDNa]. Additionally, the client-side code of a website or PWA is in most cases open source by definition, as JavaScript is an interpreted language that is executed directly from the corresponding source code. While code obfuscation and minification - that is, removing formatting and comments and shortening variable and function names - are possible and in many cases advisable to reduce the size of the page when transferred over the network, such minified JavaScript can still be analyzed and customized more readily than

an assembled and packaged binary application. An exception to this is WebAssembly (WASM) code, which can be compiled from a multitude of source languages and subsequently executed directly in the browser. However, WASM is typically only used in cases where the performance of the JavaScript interpreter is insufficient for the task, or software that was originally written for a different platform is to be executed directly in the browser. Another feature built into modern browsers that is highly useful for secure local IoT control is the *Web Crypto subtle* API, which implements select cryptographic primitives for the in-browser use. However, particularly with devices that do not support transport encryption, one has to first carefully consider whether cryptography code downloaded from the device's embedded web server and executed in the browser can be trusted.

2.2.2 Secure JavaScript cryptography code from untrusted origins

There is a theory of the so-called "Browser Cryptography Chicken and Egg Problem"[[Pta11](#)], which states that "*if you can't trust the server [or message transport] with your secrets, then how can you trust the server [or message transport] to serve secure crypto code?*"[[Mei21](#)]. Essentially, in a server and client architecture without TLS, the web page is sent to the client unencrypted. In that case, there is no easy way for one to implement client side cryptographic mechanisms without TLS communication, as all page JavaScript comes from the server and could thus be subject to a Man-in-the-Middle (MitM) attack. Therefore it is inherently untrusted and any trust in JavaScript code run on the client side would first need to be established using either built-in browser functionality, or external HTTPS servers.

Using external servers for download or verification of certain client-side code is less than ideal, as part of the availability and privacy concerns of full remote device control still apply. However it is still deemed preferable to remote control, as no user accounts are required and caching - such as possible when deployed as a PWA - may allow the solution to continue working in temporary offline conditions.

2.2.3 Secure Contexts in browsers

Another important consideration in browser-based cryptography are Secure Contexts. A multitude of powerful browser APIs are only available in Secure Contexts, i.e. when the page is loaded via TLS. This is meant to protect personal data, as access to potentially sensitive APIs, for example camera, location, or microphone, is denied. One notable API that is also only available in a Secure

Context is the aforementioned Web Crypto subtle API, which provides cryptographic primitives and useful functions, for instance the PBKDF2 schema and implementations of various hash functions. The decision to make the Subtle Crypto API only available in Secure Contexts is likely due to the fact that as outlined above, any client-side JavaScript transferred over HTTP is inherently insecure - at least without additional integrity checking of the downloaded JavaScript via trusted in-browser code. The *Subresource Integrity* feature of modern browsers supports checking the integrity of additionally downloaded JavaScript files against a hash provided in the `integrity` attribute of the `<script>` tag to be loaded. However, to the authors knowledge, such a built-in integrity check mechanism is not natively available for the root HTML page itself, therefore a trusted root page served over TLS is still required.

Furthermore, mixed content prohibition complicates interconnection between TLS and non-TLS servers, since unsecured sites may fetch additional content from TLS servers, but the inverse is not true - browsers will in general block all requests made via unsecured HTTP requests from pages loaded via HTTPS. In the context of a non-TLS capable locally controlled IoT device, approaches such as loading the control interface HTML, stylesheets, and JavaScript from a TLS-enabled external server and only establishing an HTTP connection with the device for some API control commands are therefore not trivially possible.

2.2.4 Inter-window messaging

Even though a direct HTTP or unencrypted WebSocket connection to the device from a Secure Context is disallowed by modern browsers, indirect communication is possible under certain conditions. Two different browser windows that have a mutual reference can communicate with each other using the `window.postMessage()` API to send a message and the `window.messageEvent` API to listen for incoming messages.

Note that *window* refers to a independent page context here, it does not need to be a different browser window as seen by a user, but can also be e.g. a second tab. The reference to the other window can be made by e.g. loading the second window in an `<iframe>` element embedded in the first window (though unencrypted *iframe* content is also disallowed on secure pages) and also by opening the second window in a new tab programmatically, which makes a reference to the original window available via `window.opener`, thereby allowing the opened window to send an initial message. The window message API is even available if the two windows have different origins - which often means they are hosted on different servers - and, for the JavaScript cryptography use case crucially, when one window is a Secure Context and the other is not. This

allows developers a controlled circumvention of enforced Secure Context constraints, as they can pass a message to the Secure Context window, let it process the message using an API that is only available in a Secure Context, like Web Crypto, and then return the result to the untrusted window via messaging.

2.3 Regarding the use of TLS certificates in local networks

Since it becomes clear that enabling transport layer security is the most straightforward implementation method for local device control purely from a browser context standpoint and TLS typically requires servers to identify themselves with an X.509 security certificate that should ideally have been signed by a Certificate Authority (CA) that the browser trusts, it is sensible to consider how a device in a local network may obtain a suitable TLS server certificate.

The web PKI is fundamentally designed primarily with servers reachable by the public in mind, but not local or internal networks. While established CAs that are included in default browser and operating system trust stores can issue certificates for domains and public IP addresses without problems, they are unable to issue certificates for servers running on local IPv4 networks. The reason is that a single local IPv4 address (e.g. 10.10.0.42) can not be unambiguously assigned to a single server, as all private IPv4 networks use one of the three reserved address spaces 10/8, 172.16/12, and 192.168/16[MKR+96]. This means that the same IP address is in use by an indeterminate amount of hosts on numerous different networks, and thus, attesting an unique identity is impossible based solely on the device's IP address. In the following, some methods to enable TLS in local networks and their specific implications are outlined.

2.3.1 Self-signed certificates

The most common way IoT devices that enable HTTPS for local control handle this issue is via the use of self-signed certificates. A self-signed certificate is not signed by a trusted CA, but instead by the private key that corresponds to the public key of the certificate itself. While this technically works without further configuration on the client browser side, the browser will display a prominent warning message such as the one displayed in figure 2.1 about the certificate being untrusted on first connection and every certificate change. This causes a multitude of issues for most users who are unaware of the difficulties of managing trusted TLS certificates on internal networks. Firstly, the prominent certificate warning may scare users and, given the way modern browsers display page security status, an uninitiated user may be let to believe

Figure 2.1: A prominent warning message displayed by the Edge browser upon trying to access a TLS server in the local network

that using TLS with a self-signed certificate is *less* secure than a plain unencrypted HTTP connection. Furthermore, if users become accustomed to clicking through untrusted certificate browser warnings - as that is a de-facto requirement for using TLS in local networks without further configuration - the risk of warning fatigue increases and users may disregard subsequent untrusted certificate warnings, even when they arise from an actual security issue. For example, a MitM attack between the browser and a public website would result in an identical warning, with potentially devastating consequences if the user were to accept the attacker's certificate. Therefore, proposals exist to implement different browser behavior for untrusted certificates in local networks than for certificates issued to domains or public IPs (cmp. [IoT]), but to date unfortunately no such proposal is implemented in major browsers. For instance, a behavior similar to SSH may be desirable, where upon first connection to a local server using TLS, the user would be asked whether to trust the certificate. Ideally this prompt would display a fingerprint of the public key that the user could verify against their server or IoT device out-of-band for added security. Only if the certificate subsequently changes for the same IP address, the prominent untrusted certificate warning is raised.

2.3.2 Operating a custom PKI

An alternative to self-signed certificates in local networks is creating a personal locally trusted PKI that issues TLS certificates to devices in the local network. If the Root Certification Authority

(CA) of this local PKI is subsequently added to the browsers trust store (e.g. via group policy), the process is transparent to the browser end-user and they will not receive any warnings. However, this approach is more geared towards larger enterprises, as the local PKI must be well protected against key compromise and mis-issuance, which is beyond the resources of almost all home users and even many smaller organizations.

The fact that there is no established web framework for automatic trust establishment for web based local applications is a major obstacle in particular for securing user-facing applications for use with standard browsers in internal networks, like IoT device control.

2.3.3 TLS with pre-shared key

The TLS v1.3 specification contains a "PSK-only" mode that allows for one of the defined symmetric cipher suites - e.g. `TLS_CHACHA20_POLY1305_SHA256` - to be used with a PSK that has been shared via a secure out-of-band channel without the need for any public-key cryptography. However, this functionality is primarily intended for efficient session resumption and there could be no indication found that a major browser currently supports PSK-only TLS or will do so in the future, much less derive the PSK from a user-provided password, about which RFC8446 remarks that "Deriving a shared secret from a password or other low-entropy sources is not secure" ([Res18], p. 16). Therefore, utilizing PSK-only TLS within ubiquitous browser technology is currently not feasible, however if a purely symmetric user authentication method using standard-compliant TLS v1.3 PSK is ever added, its properties and higher scrutiny would likely make it preferable to most custom implementations such as the one demonstrated in this work.

2.4 TLS-less client authentication mechanisms

For a server to be able to discern authorized from unauthorized users, i.e. clients, an authorized user is required to present proof of their authorization to the server. Using TLS, this proof can be a client certificate, however this is not an option without TLS. Most commonly, passwords are used for authentication, though they require both transport and storage protection measures against eavesdropping and subsequent misuse.

2.4.1 Secure password storage considerations

An essential security measure when storing login passwords on a server - which is the IoT device in this context - is not storing the password itself at all, but rather only a cryptographic digest (hash) derived from the password. Since cryptographic hashes are designed to be one-way functions, this allows for verification that the user is in possession of the password without actually storing it. When an attacker gains access to the password database or file - in the case of an IoT device, for instance by dumping its flash contents via a serial connection - they will gain knowledge of the hash and thus can impersonate the legitimate user, but they cannot generally recover the password to try using it in order to gain access to other accounts such as banking or e-commerce sites. This is relevant to protect the user even in case they re-used a password, which is unfortunately still a common occurrence as outlined above in [1.1.1](#).

Furthermore, passwords should be *salted*, that is, a random value unique to the user should be appended to the password prior to or during hashing. This helps mitigate against *rainbow table* attacks, where the hash obtained from the server can be rapidly compared to a table with pre-computed hashes of commonly used passwords. That way, unsalted low-security passwords can still be recovered from their hashes.

2.4.2 Deriving a shared key from the user password

Most servers that employ transport layer security (TLS) rely on it to transmit the cleartext password and then carry out hashing operations within the server itself. This raises the question why password hashing is not more commonly done on the client side, so that the cleartext password is at no time exposed to the server. One likely explanation may trace back to the "Browser Cryptography Chicken and Egg Problem" in the stance that if the server can not be trusted to handle the password, it can also not be trusted to serve secure cryptographic code for client-side password hashing. Another reason may be to reduce complexity or the reliance on JavaScript on the client side, or to increase performance in the combination of a slow client device and an expensive password hashing algorithm.

In an IoT device context where TLS is not available, client side password hashing becomes indispensable in order to avoid exposing the cleartext password during the unencrypted transmission between the browser and IoT device.

An option for password hashing built-in to browsers is *HTTP Digest access authentication*. It allows for client side password hashing and subsequently avoiding sending the password in the

Figure 2.2: Generic HTTP authentication popup dialog in the Firefox browser

clear without any use of JavaScript, however unfortunately it is susceptible to MitM attacks ([SYAB15], sec. 5.8). Since the connection is unencrypted, the attacker can downgrade the authentication scheme to use *HTTP Basic access authentication*, which transmits the password in the clear with a simple Base64 encoding. This manipulation is not readily detectable to the end user since the HTTP authentication dialog is rendered identically regardless whether Basic or Digest authentication is in use. Furthermore, the appearance is not customizable by the page, but is always rendered as a generic popup login dialog as shown in figure 2.2.

On a page sent via unencrypted HTTP, the JavaScript *Web Crypto* API is not available as the window is not in a secure context, therefore the built-in password based key derivation (PBKDF2) can not directly be used. It may appear at first as if one could implement their own algorithm directly in JavaScript or download it from an external server, however this is regarded impossible to accomplish in a secure manner due to the "Browser Cryptography Chicken and Egg Problem".

2.5 Discussion of non-TLS data transport security mechanisms

In order to implement confidentiality, integrity, and authenticity protected message transport, full TLS is not unconditionally required. In particular, the asymmetric key exchange steps and required buffers drive up implementation complexity and memory requirements. In cases where use of a pre-shared key (PSK) is acceptable, asymmetric cryptography is no longer required and

in principle, symmetric ciphers can be used directly. Some symmetric cipher suites that may be suitable in the context of IoT devices and JavaScript client implementations include the Advanced Encryption Standard (AES) and ChaCha20, which "is considerably faster than AES in software-only implementations, making it around three times as fast on platforms that lack specialized AES hardware" ([NL18], p. 3), a property that is very useful on constrained devices with low processing power that lack dedicated AES hardware. ACORN and Ascon are noteworthy families of symmetric ciphers that are designed to be particularly lightweight, with the latter being first choice in the 2019 CAESAR competition for symmetric ciphers in the category for lightweight ciphers[Ber19].

In applications where confidentiality is not required, data encryption can be omitted entirely, as for integrity and authenticity protection a cryptographically secure message authentication code (MAC) is sufficient. This increases performance compared to data encryption, as calculating a cryptographic digest (hash) of the data and authenticating it is typically significantly faster than encrypting the entire message.

A widely used MAC is HMAC. The integrity of a message can be asserted by the sender calculating $HMAC(msg, psk)$ and including the resulting hash in the transmission. The receiver, which also possesses the PSK, may now repeat this calculation, if the calculated hash matches the one included by the sender, it is valid and the receiver can be assured that the message has not been tampered with and originated from someone who knows the PSK.

2.5.1 Key differences between MAC and digital signatures

While message authentication codes and digital signatures can both be used to assert the authenticity and integrity of a message, digital signatures based on asymmetric cryptography also provide non-repudiation. As long as the sender's private key can be assumed not to be compromised, this property can be used to prove that a message was indeed sent by the sender and not by a third party. In contrast, with symmetric MACs, in order to verify the MAC, the receiver needs to possess the same symmetric pre-shared key used by the sender to authenticate the message. However, this also means that the receiver, possessing the PSK, could trivially generate valid MACs for arbitrary messages. Thus, if non-repudiation is required, MACs based on symmetric cryptography are usually not a suitable option.

2.6 Replay attacks

There is one remaining major issue with using message authentication codes like HMAC for authenticity protection in e.g. a control API. Consider an access control system where the "Open Door" message is authenticated as such:

$$\text{HMAC}(\text{"opensesame"}, \text{psk})$$

The authenticity assurance *is* valid, though if an attacker records the unencrypted legitimate transmission, they will be able to replay it at will and gain access. While the attacker is still unable to forge arbitrary messages without knowledge of the PSK, they can repeat any actions carried out by legitimate users that they have recorded.

In order to prevent replay attacks, the MAC must change every time a message is sent, even if its content is identical. The receiver must reject any messages re-transmitted with the same MAC. An effective way to facilitate changing the MAC is by the use of *nonces* (number used once). The nonce can be anything as long as it is not re-used and the receiver has means to verify a given nonce was not used before. Some possible methods for implementing nonces are described below and their impact on implementation complexity are outlined.

2.6.1 Timestamps as nonce

Including a **timestamp** as part of the message is a simple way of implementing a nonce without reliance on high-quality random number generation or more complexity in communication protocols. This way of using nonces has minimal memory requirements on both sender and receiver side, since any message with a timestamp older than a configurable interval - usually a few seconds to account for clock inaccuracies and for network message transport duration - is rejected. This only leaves a small window of time for an attacker to mount a replay attack. In some applications, this is already sufficient to mitigate the risk associated with replay attacks. A possible addition is a small list of recently used MACs that are blacklisted to further reduce the risk of a re-transmitted message being accepted. Besides a small amount of extra memory on the receiver side, this does require that no two identical legitimate messages can be processed with the same timestamp, albeit when using millisecond or better timestamp precision, this becomes a largely theoretical concern. The primary disadvantage of this timestamp-based nonce approach is that the sender and receiver both need a secured and accurate clock. If it is possible for an attacker to set the time remotely, for example via intercepting NTP (Network Time Protocol) packets, which use unsecured UDP, they can for instance set the receiver time to the timestamp

of a recorded message and thus defeat the replay protection.

2.6.2 Session IDs with counter

A slightly more complex method that does not rely on the current time is a nonce made up of two parts, a **Session ID** and a **counter**. The session ID is a random number issued by the receiver upon initial connection, thus a bidirectional connection is required. A different ID must be used for each session, so the random number must be sufficiently large - e.g. 16 bytes - to make re-use exceedingly improbable. Once the sender has obtained a session ID, they will include it together with an incrementing counter. The receiver will only accept messages with a known session ID and a given range of counter values. Usually, implementing a sliding window of acceptable counter values rather than just the value of the last received message plus one is helpful to account for possible dropped packets or transmissions arriving out-of-order. However, the receiver does need to keep track of any used counter values within the accepted window to prevent re-use. A sufficiently seeded random number generator (RNG) is required, as re-using session IDs once again enables replay attacks.

2.6.3 Counter only

A simpler approach is to omit session IDs and use just an incrementing counter with a sliding window. This has the advantage of relying neither on accurate timekeeping nor on a secure RNG. However, it requires the receiver to persistently store the lowest acceptable counter value. It is also difficult to manage multiple senders, as accidental nonce re-use is probable and in high-traffic scenarios, the sender would need to query the current counter value before each message.

2.6.4 Nonce whitelist

Another approach is the receiver randomly generating a list of nonces - which is sent to potential senders - and accepting only nonces on this list. Once a sender uses a nonce, it is replaced by a new one. By using a list with as many nonce entries as practically feasible within memory and message size constraints, re-transmissions by multiple senders attempting to use the same nonce are reduced as much as possible.

Approach	Receiver memory use	Persistent memory	Nonce communication required	Time source required	Implementation complexity	Suitable for multi-sender
Timestamps	Low	None	No	Yes	Medium	Yes
Session IDs	Medium	None	Initial connection only	No	High	Yes
Counter only	Very low	Required	If multi-sender	No	Low	More complex
Whitelist	Medium	None	Yes	No	Medium	More complex
Blacklist	Very high	Very high	No	No	Low	Yes

Table 2.1: Comparison of nonce approaches

2.6.5 Nonce blacklist

Furthermore, it is possible for senders to generate a random nonce themselves for each message, requiring the receiver to keep a nonce blacklist of every nonce ever received and rejecting any packet with such nonce. This approach does not scale well, since persistent memory and more lookup time is required for each message.

2.6.6 Comparison of nonce approaches

In table 2.1, the different approaches to implementing nonces for mitigating replay attacks are outlined for comparison. Green fields signify desirable properties of the respective approach, red signifies drawbacks.

2.7 Introduction to WLED

WLED (backronym: Wireless Lighting Effects Driver) is an open-source software project conceived and maintained by the author since 2016, designed for the ESP8266 and ESP32 microcontroller series by Espressif Systems. It is engineered to drive a large quantity of digital individually addressable full-color LEDs; individual addressability enables each LED to be set to a different color and brightness via a serial protocol and thus enables an abundance of different lighting effects. WLED has over a hundred built-in effect modes - from simple blinking over flickering

candles and twinkling fairy lights up to complex visualizations intended to be displayed on a two-dimensional matrix of LEDs. The author previously published a work[Sch21] that implements a system for custom user-defined effects that are interpreted on-the-fly from WebAssembly (WASM) without requiring a full compilation and software update cycle, as required with native effect functions based on the C++ language. WLED offers an easy-to-use and feature complete web based control user interface, additionally native mobile applications and smart home automation system integrations are available.

The primary interface for controlling a WLED instance from external hosts such as home automation software, but also from the included web-based user interface, is the WLED JSON API, which is publicly documented in detail (cmp. [S⁺24]). For the scope of this work, it is important to note that the JSON API is available both via an HTTP endpoint (`/json`) and via a WebSocket connection. WebSocket is a protocol that is based on a persistent TCP connection and offers bi-directional messaging communication between an HTTP server and client. It can thus be used to replace resource-heavy and high latency HTTP polling for receiving status updates from the server. The syntax of a WLED JSON API command is a simple JSON object containing the keys to be set. For instance, the following command would turn on the light and set it to approximately half brightness (`bri` is an 8-bit value denoting the current overall brightness, which has a range of 0-255):

```
{
  "on": true,
  "bri": 128
}
```

The author would like to give credit to Michal Madziar of *Doyensec*, who in 2021 gave a security advisory on a buffer over-write vulnerability in the WLED API and sparked the idea to add a message authentication scheme to the WLED software.

3 Implementation

In the first section, an implementation of a TLS server on the ESP32 microcontroller series is tested for performance and practical usability concerns.

3.1 ESP32 Arduino HTTPS server

Firstly, the existing library `esp32_https_server`[\[Hes21\]](#) that implements an HTTPS webserver on the ESP32 microcontroller using the Arduino framework is tested and analyzed. The various examples provided by the library maintainer do work without problems, including generation of a self-signed TLS server certificate during runtime. Uploading a credential consisting of an X.509 certificate and associated private key is also possible to integrate the server into a custom PKI.

However, the security value of the implementation is questionable, as although it utilizes `mbedtls` for cryptographic operations, the library appears largely unmaintained, as it has not received a functional update since April 2020. Furthermore, although examples are extensive and advanced functionality like `WebSocket` is supported, the `WebSocket-Chat` example has an obvious remote code execution vulnerability. JavaScript is used to display the message sent by the other party. Since this uses `innerHTML` to set the element content instead of the more secure `textContent`, any JavaScript sent by another party participating in the chat is instantly evaluated. Although the flaw is just part of a library example, this does reduce confidence in the overall security value of the actual library implementation.

For the ESP8266, no practically usable TLS server implementation was found to be available, which is to be expected due to its severely limited memory.

Due to the infeasibility of operating a TLS server on lower-end IoT hardware and the open issue of handling local certificate management for average users, an approach based on a full TLS server being hosted on the IoT device itself is not considered further within this work.

3.2 Secure communication over HTTP

Without TLS as a viable option and the primary security objectives of integrity and authenticity in mind, an alternative demo implementation method based on message authentication codes is

Figure 3.1: High level architectural overview

implemented. In figure 3.1, a high level architecture overview of the implemented demonstrator system is given. The individual components are explained in detail in the following sections.

3.2.1 Hosting of browser-based secure cryptography

Due to the "Browser Cryptography Chicken and Egg Problem" outlined in 2.2.2, doing most cryptographic operations or even just accepting input of a user password is fundamentally insecure on pages that have been loaded via HTTP only. Thus, to avoid this problem, facilitate secure message authentication, and ensure the user password is not transmitted over an insecure connection, a trusted execution environment is required. This could for instance be a page locally stored on the user device - although loading pages from downloaded HTML/JS source files is typically not implemented in browser apps for mobile devices and is also to some degree inconvenient for users. Alternatively, it could be hosted via HTTPS on a domain the user trusts (e.g. `https://rc.wled.me`, or alternatively the user could host their own server running this page for cryptographic functionality, denoted as the "secure crypto tab" in the following.

A key goal of the system to be implemented is handling all cryptographic operations within the

browser, which has two advantages: Firstly, apart from initial WLED ESP provisioning, where the PBKDF2-derived pre-shared key needs to be stored on the ESP for HMAC verification, no secrets have to leave the user device. Second, a static web page is sufficient for hosting, which greatly simplifies deployment and allows hosting on e.g. GitHub Pages or an out-of-the-box Apache server without advanced configuration as would be necessary for a full server-side framework such as Django.

For the secure crypto tab to be able to connect to the WLED instance despite the browser's mixed content prohibition, inter-window messaging is used as explained in section 2.2.4. The user is unable to control the light by directly visiting the address of the WLED instance, instead they need to open the secure crypto tab first and open the instance user interface through it. The abbreviated code for the initial window messaging handshake is given below:

wled00/data/index.js (WLED UI, ll. 250+):

```
function onLoad() {
    //...
    if (window.opener) {
        window.opener.postMessage(
            '{"wled-ui":"onload"}', '*');
    }
    //...
}
```

WLED-SecureRemoteAccess/src/messages.ts (secure crypto tab):

```
export function handleMessageEvent(event : MessageEvent) {
  //... origin verification, error handling
  var json = JSON.parse(event.data)
  if (json['wled-ui'] === 'onload') {
    event.source!.postMessage(
      '{"wled-rc":"ready"}',
      {'targetOrigin':event.origin}
    );
  }
  // handling other message types
}
```

wled00/data/index.js (WLED UI, ll. 315+):

```
function handleWindowMessageEvent(event) {
  //... origin verification, JSON parsing
  if (json['wled-rc'] === 'ready') {
    useSRA = true;
    sraWindow = event.source;
    sraOrigin = event.origin;
  }
}
```

In the first UI code block, note the second parameter '*' in the call to `postMessage`. This sends the message to any opener window, regardless of its origin, which is necessary since browsers do not allow access to `window.opener.origin` for privacy reasons. This is not ideal, since with no initial way of verifying the opener origin, a malicious site could hypothetically link to the control UI and eavesdrop on the control commands sent. However, this is a largely theoretical concern and could also be prevented by only allowing the `rc.wled.me` origin here, at the cost of preventing users from hosting the secure crypto tab themselves on a different origin. Once the reply to the handshake message by the secure crypto tab is received, `event.origin` is accessible though and can be used for custom filtering rules.

Figure 3.2: Secure crypto tab user interface

3.2.2 Technology Stack

The ESP-side code, which expands the functionality of WLED by HMAC verification capabilities, is written in C++. The cryptographic primitive implementations for *SHA256* and *HMAC* are provided by the *ESP8266 Crypto* library, though the code is expected to be fully portable except for the ESP-specific random number generator implementation. It also provides an *AES* encryption implementation that may be useful in case the implementation is to be modified to offer confidentiality protection. Being contained in a single source file *Crypto.cpp* that is below 1.000 lines of code, it is easy to independently analyze.

The WLED web UI functionality is implemented in a single JavaScript file, *index.js*.

For the secure crypto tab, which implements all in-browser cryptographic operations, a TypeScript project is used that relies on modules to improve code structure. JavaScript modules allow for more efficient implementation of object-oriented programming concepts by for instance requiring all public functions of a module to be explicitly exported for use in other modules. Other functions are private by default. TypeScript is a superset of JavaScript that adds static typing and thus enables type checking. The *Vite* build tool is used to transpile the modules back to JavaScript that can be executed in standard browsers and merge them into a single file again. The user-facing appearance of the secure crypto tab is shown in figure 3.2.

Device	Browser	Time required
Laptop, Ryzen 7 7840HS	Firefox	208 <i>ms</i>
Laptop, Ryzen 7 7840HS	Edge	151 <i>ms</i>
Laptop, Ryzen 7 7840HS	Brave	155 <i>ms</i>
Smartphone, Snapdragon 8 Gen 2 (2023)	Firefox	157 <i>ms</i>
Smartphone, Exynos 990 (2020)	Chrome	180 <i>ms</i>
Smartphone, Snapdragon 800 (2013)	Chrome	1301 <i>ms</i>
E-Book reader, Kindle Scribe	Silk	1130 <i>ms</i>

Table 3.1: Performance of PBKDF2 using the Web Crypto API

3.2.3 PBKDF2-based PSK derived from user password

In order to avoid a potential unencrypted transmission of cleartext passwords between the browser and ESP, only a hash of the password is ever transmitted outside of the secure crypto tab. The *PBKDF2* algorithm is chosen, as it is the only algorithm available in the Web Crypto API that is suitable for deriving keys from low-entropy passwords (cmp. [MDNb]). Newer hashing algorithms designed to be used for passwords, for example *Argon2id* would be preferable as it is more resistant to GPU (graphics processing unit) and ASIC (application specific integrated circuit) supported attacks by requiring the utilization of a large amount of system memory (cmp. [BDKJ21], sec. 4).

The performance of the Web Crypto Subtle implementation of PBKDF2 was tested to ensure it is adequately slow to increase the cost of brute-force guessing attacks, but still fast enough to run on low-end mobile devices. Note that PBKDF2 only needs to run in-browser, there is no requirement to do PBKDF2 on the IoT device itself as it can be provisioned directly with the key derived from PBKDF2. The required time for the PBKDF2 algorithm on a spectrum of different mobile devices can be compared in table 3.1. All tests were done with identical parameters, a 23 byte key, 8 byte salt and 1.000.000 iterations. It can be seen that while the time taken for a single password attempt is significant, i.e. $> 150\text{ ms}$, modern device stay within the 400 *ms* *Doherty Threshold* (cmp. [Yab]) and thus within the amount of time the user perceives as quick. Even though it can be argued that a more than decade-old smartphone from 2013 or an e-book reader is not a suitable device to run in-browser password key derivation on, they also successfully complete 1.000.000 iterations of PBKDF2 within 1.5 *s*, an acceptable waiting time considering the overall user-perceived speed of these devices. Therefore, 1.000.000 iterations appear to be a suitable difficulty for the types of devices a user is likely to use to access their WLED instances.

3.2.4 Generation of the MAC

The Web Crypto API is also used for generation of the HMAC message authentication code. The TypeScript function utilized for HMAC generation is given below - note that for brevity and readability, some non-critical lines have been omitted:

WLED-SecureRemoteAccess/src/crypto.ts (secure crypto tab):

```
async function generateHMAC
  (message: string, key: CryptoKey) : Promise<string>
{
  const messageBuffer = new TextEncoder().encode(message);
  const sig = await crypto.subtle.sign('HMAC', key, messageBuffer);

  return Array.from(new Uint8Array(sig)).map(function(byte) {
    return ('0' + (byte & 0xFF).toString(16)).slice(-2);
  }).join('');
}
```

This function is a good example for how the Web Crypto API can be used. Calling the primitives is usually accomplished by a single line, though some setup code is needed, particularly to set parameters correctly and to convert formats, as the Web Crypto API only operates on byte buffers (*Uint8Array* in TypeScript). The last three lines of code in the function merely convert the returned HMAC to a hexadecimal string for sending it to the ESP over the network.

3.2.5 Transport of the HMAC

After authenticating a JSON message, the HMAC is to be sent along the message in order for the receiver to be able to verify that the sender is in possession of the pre-shared key by calculating the HMAC of the message itself and comparing it to that sent along with the message. There are multiple ways to implement such data transfer with an associated authentication code, most relevant for the application in WLED are JSON payloads either over HTTP or WebSocket. In a pure HTTP environment where JSON API commands are transmitted via a HTTP POST request, a straightforward implementation method would send the HMAC as an HTTP header, separate from the JSON payload sent in the POST request. However, this approach is not possible when using a WebSocket connection, as this is just a persistent TCP connection allowing for

bi-directional messaging. Thus, the HMAC needs to be integrated into the message itself. For this purpose, the WLED JSON API calls need to be wrapped, for this the following JSON syntax is chosen:

```
{
  "mac": "baddecafc0ffee[...]",
  "msg": {
    "on": true,
    "n": {"sid":"5e55101d[...]", "c":41}
  }
}
```

Here, the `msg` object (`{"on":true}`) is the original API command, in this case to turn on the lights. An additional key `n` is added, this is a session ID and counter-based nonce that is explained in the following. This is wrapped in another JSON object that also contains a string value `mac` containing the HMAC of the API command encoded as a hexadecimal string.

3.2.6 Verification of the HMAC

The verification of the HMAC itself - without nonce validation for replay attack mitigation - is simply implemented by re-calculating the HMAC of the message data and comparing it to the MAC sent along with the message as shown in the code snippet below:

wled00/src/crypto.cpp (WLED firmware, ll. 34+):

```
bool hmacVerify(const byte* message, size_t msgLen,
                const char* pskHex, const byte* signature) {
  byte sigCalculated[SHA256HMAC_SIZE];
  hmacSign(message, msgLen, pskHex, sigCalculated);
  if (memcmp(sigCalculated, signature, SHA256HMAC_SIZE) != 0) {
    // calculated and provided HMAC do not match
    return false;
  }
  // HMAC verification successful!
  return true;
}
```

An interesting, unanticipated challenge in the implementation is extracting the "mac" and "msg" components from the JSON-formatted message shown in the previous section 3.2.5. The JSON message received by the ESP on a network request is passed as a byte array. An unconventional, but effective solution is implemented to extract the components from the raw data, with the goal of using the minimum amount of memory. In order to use *strstr* and other standard C string manipulation methods that are required to find the positions of the JSON keys "mac" and "msg" safely, the input byte buffer needs to be converted to a zero-terminated string, i.e. an array of characters in C++. The trivial solution would be to copy the data into a string with the length of the input string +1, but with the input array being potentially above 2 kB in size, making a copy is not an option giving the highly limited available memory on the ESP8266 platform. Another approach would be to cast - i.e. convert the type of - the input bytes array to a character array, but doing so would be unsafe, as it is not zero-terminated. Writing a zero byte to the first byte in memory after the array `inputBytes[inputBytesLength]` would also be illegal, as it is an out-of-bounds write able to cause undefined behavior. The solution, while unconventional, is to overwrite the last byte of the JSON message input byte array with a zero. Given that the input is a well-formed JSON object, the last character in it should always be the final closing bracket ('}'), which is not needed for extracting the components. With this modification, the input array may safely be treated as a zero-terminated string for component value extraction.

3.2.7 Resource utilization

For a security solution for resource-constrained embedded devices to be viable in practice, it does not only need to be able to operate within the memory and computing resources available, but also leave enough resources available for the application logic to run. Especially in the case of more complex use cases such as the software WLED used as the base for the example implementation herein, as with a full web server and lighting effects engine designed to drive hundreds of individual LEDs on the ESP8266 platform with just 80 kB of available user data memory, keeping the memory usage to a minimum is a crucial requirement. The additional memory usage of the HMAC functionality implemented on the ESP-side using the SHA256 hash based on the *ESP8266 Crypto* library is determined by comparing the memory usage of a build B_{Demo} - of the revision with the commit hash `f3429a6c` that has the demo implementation integrated - with build B_{Base} of the base WLED software at the point of the commit with hash `6dc2c680`, on which the demo implemented demo was based. Both the static RAM usage as well as the flash utilization, which is equal to compiled binary size of the firmware, are considered.

Build	Static RAM usage	Flash usage	Free heap memory
B_{Base}	46752 B	885 kB	21.9 kB
B_{Demo}	47032 B	899 kB	21.3 kB
$B_{Demo} - B_{Base}$	280 B	14 kB	-0.6 kB

Table 3.2: Memory usage comparison of demo and base WLED builds.

As the static RAM usage merely includes memory use of static variables allocated at compile time, but not dynamic data allocated at runtime (e.g. with `malloc` or the C++ `new` keyword), in addition the free heap memory reported by the main UI info tab right after a reboot of the microcontroller is considered, as it denotes the available memory after persistent dynamic variables - for example the buffer holding the color of each addressed LED - have been allocated. The ESP8266 is used for this analysis, as in contrast to the ESP32 platforms due to their significantly higher amount of available memory, memory optimization is essential.

The result of the memory usage analysis is described in table 3.2. It can be observed that static RAM use only increased by 280 bytes over build B_{Base} by implementing HMAC-SHA256 in build B_{Demo} . The free heap memory decreased by approximately 600 bytes, though this value is subject to fluctuation due to factors like network packet caching. The compiled binary increases in size by 14 kB.

Furthermore, the speed of the HMAC generation is essential for keeping server response time low and therefore lead to satisfactory user perceived performance (cmp. 1.1.1 above). Therefore, the performance of the `hmacSign` method is evaluated on the target platform. To reduce variability in runtime readings due to e.g. network and LED update interrupts, the measurements are taken prior to initialization of WiFi connectivity and all other startup code except the serial console. Moreover, the time taken for 100 consecutive iterations is measured to reduce measurement interval quantization errors. The measurements are visualized in figure 3.3 for two exemplary message lengths; 16 bytes, resembling a typical short control message like `{"on":true}` for turning on the device, and 2048 bytes, which may be considered a reasonable upper estimate of the length of a full JSON API *state* object - which contains the entire device state, in the case of WLED this includes all defined areas (segments) of LEDs and their respective color and effect parameters. HMAC verification times are omitted, as all measurements are within 2% of the respective measurement for generation time. This is expected, as a trivial HMAC verification - without additional security checks e.g. for nonce re-use - is simply re-generating the HMAC of the message and comparing it to the expected MAC value.

All measured times are within approximately 3 ms per iteration, which is fast enough to not have

Figure 3.3: HMAC calculation times for 16- and 2048-byte long messages on different platforms

an impact on the perceived network response performance.

3.2.8 Replay attack mitigation

Of the different nonce-based approaches to mitigate replay attacks outlined in 2.6 above, despite its higher implementation complexity, the *Session IDs with counter* (2.6.2) approach is chosen, as it does not require a persistent state on the receiver (WLED) side, does not rely on accurate timekeeping neither on the receiver nor sender side, and is suitable for multiple authorized clients to control the device at once. Note that this is not a multi-user system per se and instead refers to multiple clients that all share the password - for example due to the user accessing the light from a phone and laptop simultaneously. The possibility of true multi-user functionality is discussed below in section 4.3.2.

The random session IDs could in principle be generated either on the sender or the receiver side, but the receiver always needs to keep track of previously used session IDs - and the last state of the counter value per ID - so they are not re-used, which would allow for replay attacks. Since this tracking would need to persist across reboots, storing the session IDs in a file would be necessary, adding complexity and potentially leading to accelerated flash memory degradation due to a high volume of writes. A simpler approach is generating a sufficiently large random value on the ESP itself and sending that to the browser as soon as the connection is (re-)established. This allows the ESP to simply discard any messages using session IDs that were not generated on the ESP after the most recent boot.

Platform	RNG register
ESP8266	0x3FF20E44
ESP32	0x3FF75144

Table 3.3: ESP-series random number generator 32-bit registers

3.2.9 Random number generation

A basic prerequisite of using the Session ID approach with random IDs generated on the ESP itself is a well-seeded cryptographically secure pseudo random number generator (CSPRNG) or a true random number generator (TRNG) on the the WLED ESP (receiver) side.

Both the ESP8266 and ESP32 microcotrollers provide registers to retrieve a random 32-bit values - see table 3.3. These registers do output a different sequence of random values after each boot, suggesting that true randomness is used to seed the underlying RNG. However, the registers can be read repeatedly at the full clock speed of the processor, containing a new random value each time, suggesting that only a seeded pseudo-random generator is used. This hypothesis is supported by the ESP32 Technical Reference Manual, which advises to "make sure at least either the SAR ADC or high-speed ADC is enabled. Otherwise, pseudo-random numbers will be returned." ([Esp24], sec. 25) While no official documentation could be found regarding the ESP8266 RNG, it is likely to be implemented in a similar manner. However, whether relying on an undocumented entropy source for a critical component of the cryptographic system is acceptable should be carefully considered on a case by case basis and is certainly suboptimal. This approach is chosen for the demo implementation as it appears to work correctly after Wi-Fi initialization, though it can not be determined with certainty that Espressif's design is not subject to any edge cases that could cause a severe reduction of entropy.

3.2.10 Nonce implementation notes

As mentioned in the above, the nonce consists of a session ID and a counter that is incremented for every message sent.

For the **session ID**, a 128 bit (16 bytes) length is chosen to balance the collision risk with the associated memory use and transmission length. The session ID is sent as a hexadecimal-encoded string, where a single character may contain the 16 different digits 0-9 and A-F and can thus encode 4 bit. Therefore, a single byte is represented by a set of two characters (e.g. FF for decimal 255), so the entire session ID is represented as a 32-character long hex string.

The **counter** is incremented by the client secure crypto tab on every message sent. The connection between the control UI tab and the WLED instance is always established either via WebSocket or HTTP. As both protocols utilize TCP for packet transport, which guarantees in-order delivery of packets, keeping track of a sliding window of allowed counter values is not required, it is sufficient for the ESP to reject any value less than or equal to the last received counter value for that session ID. For the counter, a 32-bit length is chosen, as this theoretically allows for over 4 billion messages to be authenticated before a new session ID must be used to prevent the unsigned counter from overflowing and wrapping back to 0.

The ESP keeps track of allowable nonces by storing a configurable number of session ID / counter pairs. Each pair uses 20 bytes of memory (16 bytes for the session ID and 4 bytes for the counter); the array is sorted by which session IDs were most recently used in order to enable always replacing the oldest session ID with a new one if required and the array is already full. Generally, it is advisable to replace the oldest session ID. However, if multiple session IDs are requested without ever being successfully used in a MAC-authenticated message (i.e. the counter remains at 0), it may be preferable to replace such unused session IDs first. This could mitigate against a potential "session ID exhaustion" denial of service attack, where new sessions are continually started, invalidating session IDs still in use by legitimate clients.

It is crucial that the nonce is included *within* the HMAC-authenticated message; if it was sent alongside the message, an attacker could tamper with the nonce and set it to a value that would be accepted by the ESP without invalidating the MAC.

3.2.11 Communication flow

The implemented system consists of three codebase components running independently: the secure crypto tab, the user interface tab, and the WLED firmware running on the ESP device.

There are two core interactions between the codebases - the initial login authentication and subsequent authentication of control commands. Both core interactions are visualized below. Figure 3.4 shows the initial login process, while figure 3.5 outlines the control commands authentication process. The "pipe" symbol in the UI tab denotes gateway functionality - the UI tab does not process the message itself, but just forwards it from the secure crypto tab to the ESP or vice versa, changing the message transport protocol from window messaging to WebSocket or back from WebSocket to window messaging, respectively.

3.2.12 Source code availability

All source code created for the demo implementation is open source and freely available on GitHub.

The code for the secure crypto tab is available at:

<https://github.com/Aircoookie/WLED-SecureRemoteAccess>

The secure crypto tab demo is also hosted at <https://rc.wled.me> for direct use.

The WLED branch implementing the demo is available at:

<https://github.com/Aircoookie/WLED/tree/secure-api>

This branch will be maintained for a considerable length of time. If it is ever removed, the implementation may be found using the commit reference:

<https://github.com/Aircoookie/WLED/commit/f3429a6c9355>

The *ESP8266 Crypto* library is available at:

<https://github.com/Aircoookie/arduino-crypto>

Note that this library is the work of Chris Ellis et al. and has merely been forked by the author to integrate some minor bug fixes.

4 Analysis and Conclusion

In this final chapter, it is analyzed whether the implemented solution attains the goals set out in the introduction to this thesis. Furthermore, limitations and opportunities for improvements and works expanding upon the concept demonstrated herein are outlined. Lastly, the findings are conclusively summarized and a reflection of the thesis is given.

4.1 Discussion

In the following, several aspects of the implementation are reflected upon and analyzed in terms of their advised usability in production systems and their long-term safety against quantum computing algorithms.

4.1.1 Secure production deployment of the implemented solution

While the architecture drafted and implemented in the above was continuously scrutinized on a best faith effort to be secure, it should strictly be considered a demo implementation for research and testing purposes only. The author can not guarantee the security of the implemented solution and it should only be used in practical applications once thoroughly and independently verified. Although only known and well-vetted cryptographic primitives are implemented, custom cryptographic system designs are easily prone to subtle errors that render the entire system ineffective - one example for an aspect that is not immediately obvious but essential for the security of the design is the nonce-based replay attack mitigation outlined in section [2.6](#).

4.1.2 Post-Quantum Cryptography considerations

Given future advances in quantum computing capabilities, it is feasible that the underlying primitives - usually RSA or ECC - of presently state-of-the-art asymmetric cryptography systems could be compromised, which would affect the majority of systems in use today, including the web PKI and key agreement used in TLS. Since the global societal and economical impact of an unprepared-for "Q-Day" (the point in time at which quantum computing can feasibly break current asymmetric cryptography) would be unprecedented, new post-quantum cryptography (PQC)

algorithms for key agreement and digital signatures are actively being researched and vetted. In August 2024, the US National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST) has standardized three digital signature and key encapsulation algorithms as FIPS 203 (ML-KEM), 204 (ML-DSA), and 205 (SLH-DSA) after four rounds of public feedback and improvement[[Nat24](#)].

Nonetheless, there are currently no indications that symmetric ciphers, such as AES, or MAC-based approaches, such as implemented in this work, would be meaningfully reduced in their security value by quantum-based approaches; they are therefore deemed quantum-resistant (cmp. [[PMST21](#)], p.11). Thus, given the current state of research, unlike for instance current TLS implementations, the security of the implemented solution is likely to remain unaffected by the availability of powerful quantum computing resources, which is particularly important with embedded systems such as used in IoT devices, as they are typically in use for significantly longer periods of time than traditional IT hardware such as PCs and smartphones.

4.2 Limitations

While the implemented solution demonstrates that implementing hash-based security measures is highly feasible on constrained devices with limited resources such as the ESP8266, there are some use cases and limitations not addressed by the current implementation yet.

4.2.1 Initial PSK provisioning

One core limitation that the implemented demonstrator does not yet address is the mechanism used for initial provisioning of the ESP running WLED with the pre-shared key that is derived from the user password using PBKDF2 and subsequently used as the HMAC key to generate message authentication codes. There are multiple possible approaches to securely handle such initial device provisioning processes. The scope of the general provisioning problem goes beyond just the PSK for the HMAC authentication, since the device also needs to be provisioned with the credentials to connect to the home Wi-Fi network. The core requirement for secure provisioning is an ideally mutually trusted secure channel that also uses encryption or similar means to protect confidentiality of these secrets. There are currently two standard ways to provision an ESP microcontroller running WLED.

Firstly, by default the WLED ESP opens its own Wi-Fi access point (AP) if no network to connect to is configured. The AP leverages standard WPA2 encryption and thus would in principle be suitable for provisioning the device with secrets. However, in practice this is not a secure method

as a default password (`w1ed1234`) is shared between all installations. While it makes exploitation less probable, first changing the AP password does not stop an attacker from capturing the new password and subsequently eavesdropping on the transmission of the secrets, and is also something the average user is unlikely to do as their aim is generally to set up the device as quickly and frictionlessly as possible. For manufacturers making hardware pre-installed with WLED, e.g. *QuinLED*, it may be feasible to implement a process that provisions each device with a unique AP password that is then stated on a label or QR code that comes with the hardware. This does however not solve this problem for most other users.

Another secure option for provisioning the ESP is via its serial interface instead of Wi-Fi. Due to the nature of a direct wired connection to a personal computer, the risk of eavesdropping is minimal. This approach to ensuring confidentiality of the initial provisioning secrets is best suited for do-it-yourself WLED deployments, as the installation of the firmware itself already requires a serial connection in most cases - unless the previously installed firmware has OTA update capabilities. In fact, the WLED web installer already supports provisioning the WLED instance with Wi-Fi credentials using *Improv Serial*[\[Ope\]](#), an open standard by the Open Home Foundation. A similar method could be implemented to support provisioning with the HMAC PSK as well.

Alternatively, the PSK could be transmitted over the home network after WLED connects to it. This however comes with the caveat that the user has to trust the home network and all devices attached to it. There are scenarios where WLED instances may be connected exclusively to untrusted networks - for example a shared college dormitory network - where a zero trust approach is absolutely mandatory - that is, no device is trusted merely because it has access to the network. Given that an access control system based on the architecture outlined in this work should generally have the goal of supporting both the use cases of secure remote access via e.g. port forwarding and especially also secure local access over networks that are not unconditionally trustworthy. Therefore, offering alternative means for secure provisioning, such as via a serial connection, is indispensable.

Further research that focuses on how to achieve secure initial provisioning while offering an excellent user experience especially to users with no background in cryptographic operations or general information security is essential for the implementation of a system that is able to offer a high degree of usability in practice.

4.2.2 Potential for MitM command injections

While the implemented system already significantly raises the transport security value and makes it more difficult for unauthorized parties to send valid unauthorized commands, there is still a significant risk for MitM attacks allowing for MAC verification of unauthorized commands, which again has its root in the "Browser Cryptography Chicken and Egg Problem". Although the implemented system outsources the relevant cryptographic operations to the secure crypto tab, all commands to be authenticated still originate from the untrusted control UI that is loaded from the ESP web server via insecure HTTP. This would allow the attacker to insert arbitrary control commands into the UI page source that could automatically be authenticated by the HMAC generation in the secure crypto tab and pass the ESP-side HMAC verification as regular MAC-authenticated commands.

There are multiple possible ways to address this problem. Firstly, a hash over the control UI assets could be calculated and checked against a database of known-safe UI page versions. This approach, while transparent to the end user, has two significant drawbacks. Firstly, modern browsers do not allow the secure crypto tab to access the UI page in a way that would allow for calculating e.g. its SHA256 hash. Secondly, as an open source software, the choice of customization for the user is an essential goal, and the integrity hash of any custom-made UI version will differ from versions included in the database.

Secondly, all HMAC authentication requests could be withheld in the secure crypto tab and manually be approved by the user. It is however highly impractical to expect users to swap tabs and approve a command any time they want to change a value in the web UI. Furthermore, without specific knowledge of the JSON API structure utilized by WLED, the average user would also likely be unable to distinguish the JSON of their valid request from a different one crafted by an attacker. Therefore, manual command approval is not a practically viable solution.

Lastly, the entire control UI could be hosted in the secure crypto tab, which would ensure no MitM command injection would be possible. The page loaded from the ESP web server over the insecure HTTP connection would be reduced to acting as a gateway that receives the window message from the secure crypto tab and passing it to the ESP via the WebSocket connection. This approach has the least drawbacks, although one is still significant, namely the secure crypto tab must have a version of the UI available that is API-compatible with the WLED version installed on the ESP. While this may be straightforward for standard builds, it would once again make it difficult for developers of custom features to have their version of the UI used by the secure crypto tab. This problem could be in part alleviated by allowing the ESP to specify a URL where

a compatible version of the UI is hosted. While this approach requires retrieving the UI via that URL and incurs the associated limitations regarding availability of online services, this URL could be part of the ESP-side firmware and also be protected against MitM URL replacement attacks using an HMAC generated on the ESP side.

4.2.3 Side channel attacks

One possible attack vector, particularly for sophisticated attackers, are side channel attacks. Side channel attacks can be used to compromise a system by observing subtle differences in a systems behavior, for example in the time it takes to return an error message or fluctuations in its power draw. Side channel attacks were not considered in this demo implementation. As an example, the hash comparison shown during HMAC verification shown in the code snippet in section 3.2.6 short-circuits if a character does not match, which causes the `memcmp` function to take a few clock cycles longer to return for every character starting from the beginning of the two hashes that match. If an attacker has the ability to observe these small differences in execution time, they can use this to deduce the correct MAC for a given message byte by byte. In this particular case, replacing `memcmp` against a cryptographically secure hash comparison function would prevent this specific attack by always taking a constant time to compare the hashes, regardless of the number of characters that match between the hashes. Similar considerations need to be taken into account for other conditional logic as well to mitigate against common types of side channel attacks.

4.3 Further research and outlook

The implemented demo underlines the lightwightness of the HMAC-based message protection, being able to run even on platforms with extremely low amounts of RAM available for cryptographic schemes. Nonetheless, there are several opportunities to expend upon this research in the future, a selection of which are outlined below.

4.3.1 Authenticated OTA software update

The demonstrator implemented in this work shows the feasibility of using message authentication code to secure the JSON control API against both deliberate and unintentional integrity violations. Another essential capability of IoT devices is to perform over-the-air (OTA) software updates -

either to add new functionality, fix bugs or, most crucially, remediate security issues found in the solution. OTA updates are a particularly noteworthy interface, since when exploitable by an attacker, they allow for easily running arbitrary firmware and thus taking control of the device, infiltrating the user's network, or making the device participate in a botnet for large scale targeted DDoS (Distributed Denial of Service) and similar attacks. Therefore, the implemented system should be augmented to cover authenticated OTA firmware updates. The proposed authentication system would be implemented like the following: The user uploads the new firmware file to the secure crypto tab, where its SHA256 hash is calculated. Then the update is authenticated with a MAC-authenticated JSON API message containing the hex-encoded hash of the firmware update file, for instance the following:

```
{
  "mac": "c0ffee15900d[...]",
  "msg": {
    "auth-ota-hash": "1533dc0ffee[...]",
    "n": {"sid": "5e55101d[...]", "c": 42}
  }
}
```

This separate two-step hashing is an effective method to avoid including the entire firmware update binary within the JSON API message, which would not be feasible in practice due to the size of firmware updates, which for WLED version 0.15.0-b5 is approximately 900 *kB* for a ESP8266 and 1.5 *MB* for an ESP32 binary of the compiled firmware, respectively. The firmware update binary file may subsequently be sent unprotected. Before installation, the ESP then verifies the hash of the downloaded binary against the one previously authenticated via the API message and only installs the update if this authentication is successful. Although it may not seem so on first impression as only authorized firmware passes, a nonce-based replay attack mitigation is also required for firmware updates. Otherwise, a downgrade attack is possible, where an attacker can revert to any previously authorized firmware version they captured the authentication message for. While a downgrade attack does not directly allow for arbitrary code execution, the previous firmware version may have contained an exploitable bug that the attacker is again able to use after a successful firmware downgrade.

4.3.2 Multiple users and role-based access management

It could be an interesting addition to augment the implemented system with support for multiple users and even role-based access to only part of the IoT device capabilities. For example, there could be users with access to just the lighting control, while settings and firmware updating capabilities would only be accessible for users bearing the admin role. The HMAC-based system is deemed flexible enough to support multiple users by adding a user identifier such as a username and selecting the PSK and salt from the protected file stored in the ESP file system accordingly. This is a compelling topic for further research, as despite role-based privileged access control being widespread in many applications, it is seldomly employed in constrained embedded devices, where often a single account grants access to all device functionality indiscriminately.

4.3.3 Revisiting TLS

As hosting a TLS server on the ESP32 platform was found to be feasible in principle, it would be valuable to further study whether a practical implementation is feasible, for example by integrating the ESP32 HTTPS web server library into an open source IoT project such as WLED and evaluating performance, client side certificate validation methods and exploring considerations for an effective certificate lifecycle management.

4.4 Conclusion

In the course of this work, two core strategies for achieving local IoT device control using standard web browsers were successfully analyzed, as defined in the research objectives in section 1.2.

Firstly, hosting a **TLS server** on the IoT device itself was demonstrated to be feasible at least on modern IoT devices based on a more powerful platform such as the ESP32. However, due to issues with the way the average user would likely perceive the way browsers warn against self-signed certificates in local networks, the inability to obtain public CA certificates for local hosts, and the infeasibility of regular users hosting a custom PKI, as well as the infeasibility of a TLS server on lower end devices like the ESP8266, a TLS server hosted directly on the device is regarded as not a viable option for many local IoT deployments.

Secondly, **alternative** methods for securing the control command communication between the user browser and IoT device were identified, aiming to be more **lightweight** than a TLS server implementation. It was found that approaches involving purely symmetric ciphers with a pre-shared

key can be feasible depending on the requirements of the specific application. Furthermore, message authentication codes are a viable option in cases where message integrity and authenticity protection are required, but confidentiality protection is not needed, which greatly reduces the amount of necessary computation and memory resources that would be needed for encipherment and decryption; and thus is an excellent candidate for implementation on constrained devices that do not handle sensitive data. As the WLED software meets these criteria, an HMAC-based command message authentication scheme was successfully realized in a proof-of-concept demonstrator implementation that uses particularly few resources - less than a kilobyte of additional RAM usage was observed for the HMAC functionality. Moreover, novel methods to securely use cryptographic functionality in client browsers - even when the connection to the IoT device itself is untrusted - were designed. This results in an overall more user-friendly implementation compared to a direct TLS server.

Conclusively, the research goal of this thesis could be fully met. Multiple approaches for local device control that are supported by standard browsers were successfully identified and implemented. Despite undebatable hurdles system designers face when designing local control schemes that are to both interoperate fully with standard browsers and be functional on resource constrained devices, the work demonstrated that a practically usable and secure implementation of a lightweight web-based local IoT control system is definitely feasible. Once further refined and more widely deployed, a similar solution to that implemented herein has the potential to elevate the IoT ecosystem towards a vision that enables complete privacy, choice and sustainability for device owners.

Sources & Literature

- [BDKJ21] BIRYUKOV, Alex ; DINU, Daniel ; KHOVRATOVICH, Dmitry ; JOSEFSSON, Simon: *Argon2 Memory-Hard Function for Password Hashing and Proof-of-Work Applications*. RFC 9106. <http://dx.doi.org/10.17487/RFC9106>. Version: 2021 (Request for Comments) 26
- [Ber19] BERNSTEIN, D. J.: *CAESAR submissions*. <https://competitions.cr.yp.to/caesar-submissions.html>. Version: 2019 16
- [CMN83] CARD, Stuart K. ; MORAN, Thomas P. ; NEWELL, Allen: *The Psychology of Human-Computer Interaction*. 1983 <https://doi.org/10.1201/97802037361663>
- [Esp24] ESPRESSIF SYSTEMS: *ESP32 Technical Reference Manual*. https://www.espressif.com/sites/default/files/documentation/esp32_technical_reference_manual_en.pdf#rng. Version: 2024 32
- [Goo24] GOOGLE: *Support for Nest Secure ended*. <https://support.google.com/googlenest/answer/10191961?hl=en>. Version: 2024 3
- [Hes21] HESSEL, Frank: *ESP32 HTTPS Server*. https://github.com/fhessel/esp32_https_server. Version: 2021 21
- [IoT] IOT SECURITY FOUNDATION: *Change Browser Behaviour*. <https://specs.manysecured.net/suib/Solutions/browser-solution/> 12
- [MDNa] MDN WEB DOCS: *Progressive web apps*. https://developer.mozilla.org/en-US/docs/Web/Progressive_web_apps 8
- [MDNb] MDN WEB DOCS: *SubtleCrypto: deriveKey() method*. <https://developer.mozilla.org/en-US/docs/Web/API/SubtleCrypto/deriveKey> 26
- [Mei21] MEIXLER TECHNOLOGIES INC.: *Browser Crypto*. <https://www.pageintegrity.net/browsercrypto.php>. Version: 2021 9
- [MKR⁺96] MOSKOWITZ, Robert ; KARRENBERG, Daniel ; REKHTER, Yakov ; LEAR, Eliot ; GROOT, Geert J.: *Address Allocation for Private Internets*. RFC 1918. <http://dx.doi.org/10.17487/RFC1918>. Version: 1996 (Request for Comments) 11
- [Nat24] NATIONAL INSTITUTE OF STANDARDS AND TECHNOLOGY: *Post-Quantum Cryptography*

- tography*. <https://www.nist.gov/pqcrypto>. Version: 2024 37
- [NL18] NIR, Yoav ; LANGLEY, Adam: *ChaCha20 and Poly1305 for IETF Protocols*. RFC 8439. <http://dx.doi.org/10.17487/RFC8439>. Version: 2018 (Request for Comments) 16
- [Ope] OPEN HOME FOUNDATION: *Improv Wi-Fi is an open standard for connecting devices to Wi-Fi using Bluetooth LE or Serial*. <https://www.improv-wifi.com/> 38
- [Ope24] OPEN HOME FOUNDATION: *About us*. <https://www.openhomefoundation.org/about/>. Version: 2024 4
- [PMST21] PREUSS MATTSSON, John ; SMEETS, Ben ; THORMARKER, Erik: *Quantum-Resistant Cryptography*. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2112.00399>. Version: 2021 37
- [PPG24] PAAR, Christof ; PELZL, Jan ; GÜNEYSU, Tim: *Understanding Cryptography*. Springer Berlin, Heidelberg, 2024 https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-662-69007-9_6
- [Pta11] PTACEK, Thomas: *Javascript Cryptography Considered Harmful*. <https://gist.githubusercontent.com/atoponce/e90089cb5a13ef38a7a07f8e64370dab/raw/22299b4e722840f955ebc3d65d6ec040811601f1/post.md>. Version: 2011 9
- [Res18] RESCORLA, Eric: *The Transport Layer Security (TLS) Protocol Version 1.3*. RFC 8446. <http://dx.doi.org/10.17487/RFC8446>. Version: 2018 (Request for Comments) 13
- [S⁺24] SCHWINNE, Christian u. a.: *JSON API*. <https://kno.wled.ge/interfaces/json-api/>. Version: 2024 20
- [Sch21] SCHWINNE, Christian: *Design and implementation of a full-stack web scripting environment facilitating performance and memory usage optimized dynamic user-provided code execution in a network-enabled embedded lighting effect control application context*. 2021 <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14038778> 20
- [Ste18] STEIGERWALD, Michael: *Smart Home - Smart Hack*. https://media.ccc.de/v/35c3-9723-smart_home_-_smart_hack#t=728. Version: 2018 2, 8
- [SYAB15] SHEKH-YUSEF, Rifaat ; AHRENS, David ; BREMER, Sophie: *HTTP Digest Access Authentication*. RFC 7616. <http://dx.doi.org/10.17487/RFC7616>. Version: 2015 (Request for Comments) 15

- [Tuy] TUYA INC.: *Security and Compliance*. <https://www.tuya.com/rule> 2
- [WJH⁺18] WANG, Chun ; JAN, Steve T. ; HU, Hang ; BOSSART, Douglas ; WANG, Gang: *The Next Domino to Fall: Empirical Analysis of User Passwords across Online Services*. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3176258.3176332>. Version: 2018 3
- [Yab] YABLONSKI, Jon: *Doherty Threshold*. <https://lawsofux.com/doherty-threshold/> 26

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Hamm, den 6. November 2024

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